

Mechanical and surface characterization of Drug Coated Balloons

Deepthishre Gunashekar¹, Dario Gastaldi¹, Giancarlo Pennati¹, Pasquale Vena¹

¹ Department of Chemistry, Materials and Chemical engineering, Politecnico di Milano, Milan, Italy

* deepthishre.gunashekar@polimi.it

INTRODUCTION

Angioplasty balloons have been in use for decades to treat Arteriosclerosis. Factors like inflammation, increase in blood pressure, increase in blood cholesterol level and vascular wall injury during angioplasty leads to the increase in the thickness of the vessel wall, which is otherwise called intimal hyperplasia¹. To reduce this restenosis from happening, procedures are performed using drug coated balloons (DCBs) with a highly lipophilic, antiproliferative drug that helps in preventing the smooth muscle cell proliferation and excipient which acts as the carrier for the drug. Paclitaxel and Sirolimus are the two drugs that are commercially used by the manufacturers due to its cytostability in therapeutic dosages. However, there still is a problem of high rates of drug wash off resulting in very low drug transfer, i.e., 10-18% of the initial drug concentration loaded on the balloon². Thus, it is important to study the characteristics of the balloon material and the drug to understand the drug transfer process. Not many studies have been done on characterizing the balloon properties and mechanical stability of the coating loaded with drugs. In this research the physico-mechanical properties and surface characteristics are studied on the different coated and non-coated balloon materials.

EXPERIMENTAL METHODS

An ideal balloon material should be biocompatible, strong and puncture resistant to overcome the frictional and elastic forces during the procedure. It is also important for the balloon surface to be able to hold the drug in place and release when necessary. Balloon material should be stronger in the radial direction than the axial direction to have a higher burst strength³. Both Uniaxial and Bi-axial tensile testing were performed along with bulge testing to analyze the compliance of the balloon and the influencing parameters. Both dry and wet conditions were considered to mimic the in-vivo conditions. Surface characterizations were done with the help of confocal laser microscopy and Scanning Electron Microscopy.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The mechanical analysis suggested that the properties of the balloon vary at different regions of the balloon and with respect to inflation rate. Figure 1 shows the stress-strain curves of the angioplasty balloons at different regions and different strain rates. The morphology of the Pebax balloon surfaces were recorded under the confocal microscopy, shown in Figure 2. The thickness of the balloon was observed to be varying from 48.3 μ m to 52.6 μ m along the length of the balloon by observing the intensity at the interfaces and refractive index of the balloon material was also analyzed with the help of step measurement. These observations under various stress conditions helped to understand the damage tolerance of the balloon and fragmentation of the drug coating.

Figure 1: Circumferential stress-strain analysis from ring test.

Figure 2: Surface characterization under confocal laser microscope. (a) Color coded height-map representation of balloon thickness using step measurement and (b) Film thickness measurement by analyzing the light intensity difference between the substrate and balloon surface

CONCLUSION

In this study, a preliminary analysis on the physical and mechanical properties of angioplasty balloons under various stress conditions are presented. Influence of fiber orientations and ratio of the polymers were also observed. The final aim of the study was to verify whether by adjusting the mechanical and physical parameters, we can achieve high mechanical stability of the drug on the balloon surface which will certainly increase the drug release to the targeted area.

REFERENCES

1. J. Charles Jennette, J. R. S. et al., 197-219, 2014.
2. Cremers B, B. G. et al., Euro Intervention. 2140-2147, 20174.
3. Warner JA, F. B. et al., J. Biomed Part B, 470– 475, 2016.

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement No 956470.